

Flipped Learning in Schools: A Systematic Literature Review and Future Challenges

Dr. Nida Khan

Assistant Professor, Department of Teacher Education, Vardhaman College, Bijnor

Dr. Dharmendra Kumar

Professor, Department of Teacher Education, Vardhaman College, Bijnor

ABSTRACT

Flipped learning has emerged as a pedagogical innovation in education that includes active participation and personalized learning. The flipped classroom (FC) model inverts traditional teaching methods by imparting direct instruction outside the classroom and using class time for active learning. In India, where population itself challenges education. There are several challenges in education like overcrowded classrooms, rote learning, teacher student ratio, limited interaction between teachers and students and lack of infrastructural facilities. The flipped classroom model helps in minimizing these challenges. This paper provides a systematic review of the literature on flipped learning in schools. Paper examines pedagogical benefits, implementation challenges, and the impact of flipped learning on students and teachers. A thematic analysis of recent studies reveals flipped learning enhances student participation and understanding in classroom. The only challenges that hinder the progress of flipped learning includes limited technology access, teacher preparedness and curriculum integration. The paper concludes with recommendations of further research and also discussion of future challenges.

Keywords: *Flipped Learning, Systematic Review, Future Challenges*

INTRODUCTION

The flipped classroom (FC) model was first introduced by Jonathan Bergmann and Aaron Sams in 2007 in high school for teaching of science classrooms in the United States. The flipped classroom model reverses the traditional teaching method by engaging students in content delivery through online videos or reading materials outside the class and using in-class time for active learning, discussions, problem-solving, and collaborative work. This pedagogical approach promotes deeper understanding, enhances engagement of students, and increase interaction between students and teachers. In this approach, students access instructional content outside the classroom provided by the teacher and engage in discussions and collaborative learning during class time with peers and teacher. Thus, this model foster student-centric learning and also critical and logical thinking skills in students which is the need of 21st-century education (Bergmann & Sams, 2012).

In traditional classroom setting teacher stands in front of blackboard while students sit in front of teacher in rows and listen. Students open their books and follow what teacher says. Few of students look bored and distracted in classroom. Collaboration has been limited in traditional classrooms. Individual had to buy book or issue book for their learning. Today massive information is available through internet. Thus, technology in education as an approach focuses on student centric education and is a key to move in 21st century education.

In India, where the education system is denoted by large student-teacher ratios, little teacher-student interaction, rote learning and lack of infrastructural facilities, the flipped classroom holds potential to overcome these challenges (Bergmann & Sams, 2012). With advancement of technology in each section such as increasing access to smartphones, enhanced internet connectivity, and opportunities to new digital tools, the introduction of Flipped Classroom in Indian schools in urban and semi-urban areas has become more feasible. However, the model's adoption faces several challenges, especially in rural areas it remains a significant barrier due to lack of technological infrastructure in schools. Apart from rural areas challenges, the implementation of flipped learning in schools faces several other challenges such as incongruity in technological access, teacher preparedness, and difficulties in line up flipped approach with Indian curriculum.

This paper analyses existing research on flipped learning model in schools, identify central ideas, and investigate future challenges. The structure of paper follows methodology, findings, discussion, future challenges, and conclusion. This paper presents a comprehensive review of the flipped classroom model in Indian schools. It examines the implementation, effectiveness, and future challenges of flipped learning pedagogical approach in the context of Indian schools.

FLIPPED CLASSROOM: KEY FEATURES

Flipped Classroom is an inverting or flipping a class approach that intentionally invert lectures, content and asynchronous activities into an online and out-of-class learning environment. In this model teachers use face-to-face class time for active learning that increase student engagement, deepen understanding of concepts and advance mastery of skills.

Flipped Classroom involves FLIP approach. FLIP approach involves four pillars. These four pillars are the foundation of an effective flipped classroom.

Flexible Environments: Flexible Environments in a flipped model not only refers to the physical learning spaces, i.e. small groups, team work, but also refers to the flexibility that what content will be taught in the classroom and what content should be taught outside of the classroom. They create flexible and hybrid learning spaces in which students choose when and where they learn. In flipped model, students have a much more flexible view of student learning.

Learning Culture: The learning culture represents the second pillar of the Flipped model. The learning culture in a flipped model is a paradigm shift in teaching and learning. Here the teacher worked as facilitator. Creating in-class activities that measured students understanding of the concept and achievable based on the learning that takes place outside of the classroom is a critical component of the learning culture.

Intentional Content: Intentional content is all about choosing the best content to be delivered inside and outside of the classroom. In a Flipped Classroom, Remembering and Understanding are moved outside of the classroom and Creating, Analysing and Applying in the classroom. During Flipped Learning, teachers are constantly thinking about how they can use the Flipped Learning model to help students develop greater understanding of key concepts, and then how and when to best use this knowledge. Intentional Content is a process to maximize classroom time in order to adopt effective pedagogy alongside student-centered, active learning strategies, depending on grade level and subject matter.

Professional Educators: Teacher has an even bigger role to play in Flipped Classrooms that involves significant responsibilities. Teachers have responsibility to continuously observe their students, provide relevant and timely feedback, and assess their work. Teachers need to be reflective in their practice and should connect with each other to develop the quality in their classrooms. Teachers have prominent roles in a flipped classroom that enables Flipped Learning to occur successfully.

The flipped classroom model is a radical shift from traditional teaching methods that based on the "sage on the stage" approach where the teacher is the primary source of knowledge. In the Flipped Classroom model, students are go through with lecture content through videos, articles, reading material before coming to class and thus during class time they are engaged in interactive and student-centered learning (Bergmann & Sams, 2012). Researches done in various countries like the United States and Canada, showed that the Flipped

Classroom model increases student engagement, improves learning outcomes, and allows for more individualized learning (Zainuddin & Perera, 2019).

A key feature of the flipped classroom model is the prominent use of technology to provide asynchronous learning materials with new idea. Learning materials may include instructional videos, reading materials, quizzes, and interactive assignments. Thus, class time is then effectively used for interactive learning activities, such as group discussions, team teaching, project work and problem-solving tasks that involves maximum participation of the students in teaching and learning. Studies have shown that Flipped Classroom can effectively helpful in enhancing critical thinking, understanding concepts, collaborative work and student centric learning (Zainuddin & Perera, 2019).

METHODOLOGY

Search Strategy: Systematic literature review follows the PRISMA framework (Moher et al., 2009). Articles/papers were retrieved from databases of Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. Keywords such as "flipped learning," "flipped classroom," "flipped education," and "invert teaching" were used.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Systematic review includes peer-reviewed papers/articles published between 2010 to 2023. Studies focusing on school education were included. Studies focusing on higher education were excluded.

Data Collection and Analysis: Data were collected based on the concepts of flipped learning such as pedagogical benefits, challenges, applications and effects on academic performance. Thematic analysis was used to synthesize research findings (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

FINDINGS

- **Academic Gain:** Research studies highlight that flipped learning enhanced engagement of students in classroom and foster interactive learning environment. Students who learned using flipped classroom model often shows better critical thinking and problem-solving skills. They also demonstrate substantial autonomy in learning (Lo & Hew, 2017). Collaborative activities inside the classroom also deepen understanding of concepts and promote peer learning (Chen et al., 2018).
- **Implementation Challenges:** Flipped learning faces significant challenges such as access to technology in underprivileged section (Kim et al., 2014). Lack of skills in teachers to create high-quality instructional content that meet the diverse need of students (Bergmann & Sams, 2012).
- **Applications related to Subjects:** Flipped learning has been widely used in various subjects. STEM education shows significant impact of flipped learning. Flipped approaches in mathematics and science enhanced the conceptual understanding of subject and also the application skills (Chen et al., 2018). However, applications in humanities and arts are less documented, indicating a need for further research (Lo & Hew, 2017).
- **Students Perspectives:** The majority of studies highlights positive impacts on student academic performance. Students feel motivated and confident. They actively participate in class activities. However, some studies shows that students unfamiliar to self-directed learning struggled initially with the flipped classroom model (Kim et al., 2014).
- **Teachers Perspectives:** Teachers taken flipped learning positively but express their concerns regarding resources required and time for preparation of instructional material. Professional training and technological support are essential for teachers to effectively implement this flipped classroom model in their teaching (Bergmann & Sams, 2012).

OPPORTUNITIES FOR FLIPPED LEARNING IN INDIAN CONTEXT

India's education system has undergone significant changes over the past few decades but still faced numerous challenges. There are several challenges that the flipped classroom model would overcome:

- **Jam-packed Classrooms:** Several schools in India have large number of students. Thus, it is very difficult for teachers to pay attention to each student. The flipped classroom could lessen this problem by shifting mode of content delivery outside of class and using in class time for more focused and interactive learning (Hwang & Lai, 2016).
- **Teacher-Centric Pedagogy:** Schools in India are teacher-centered. Teacher delivers lectures in the classroom and students follow the same. The flipped classroom is a paradigm shift from teacher-centered learning to student-centered learning that helps in fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills in students (Sharma & Ghosh, 2019).
- **Parroting:** In Indian classrooms often, students memorize the concepts instead of understanding the same. They are passive in classroom participation. By flipping the classroom, students have to go through the content on their own, thus they have meaningful learning experiences (Rao, 2020).
- **Limited Student Engagement:** Traditionally, students follow the teacher in Indian schools. But by flipped classroom students are more engaged instead of passive and inactive learners. They take part in discussions and peer learning as active member (Rao,2020)
- **Technological Access:** Digital divide is a significant challenge in Indian Scenario in rural and underprivileged sections. But increasing access to smartphones and laptops in urban areas offers an opportunity to introduce flipped classrooms. Initiatives by government such as "Digital India" campaign have enhanced digital literacy but gaps still exist in rural and underserved areas (Tiwari & Shah, 2021).

Therefore, despite several challenges in schools of India, the flipped classroom has substantial potential to reshape the learning environment and learning pattern.

IMPLEMENTATION OF FLIPPED CLASSROOM MODEL IN RURAL AND URBAN SCHOOLS

The flipped classroom model has several benefits that overcome the challenges of Indian schools. The implementation of flipped classroom model in Indian settings divide in two categories as Rural and urban schools. Most of the Indian population live in rural areas. Thus, to bring change in Indian education system we thoroughly work in rural settings. The Several studies show the remarkable change in rural and urban schools in adopting the flipped classroom model. Some studies analysis is given below:

Urban Schools

Metropolitan Cities count in urban areas. In metropolitan cities like Delhi, Mumbai, and Bengaluru, the progressive schools implemented flipped classroom model has been in subjects of mathematics, science, and languages. For example, The Shri Ram School in Delhi has implemented flipped learning in the middle and high school grades as experiment. They used platforms like Google Classroom and YouTube to provide pre-recorded lessons for out of class learning. Teachers then use classroom time in several group activities like discussions and peer learning. Result highlights that after applying flipped classroom model the participation and engagement of students has increased in overall learning (Tiwari & Shah, 2021).

Similarly, in Mumbai, The VIBGYOR high school also experimented flipped learning in science. They provide video-lessons on topics of physics and chemistry for out of class learning. Then they use their class time on hands-on experiments, group discussions, projects and problem-solving tasks. They found their students more active and interactive in overall learning. Lastly, they take feedback from students and found overwhelmingly positive responses from the students. They quoted that they understand complex concepts very easily (Sharma & Ghosh, 2019).

Rural Areas

In rural areas, the implementation of flipped classrooms model is obstructed by limited access of speedy internet connections and lack of proper digital devices. According to a report by Rao (2020), many schools in rural areas of India have poor infrastructure that leads difficulty in installing and maintaining digital tools. Financial crisis and lack of proper digitally trained teachers are other challenges of remote areas. In these areas, due to the lack of digital resources like computers, projectors, printers and speedy internet connection, the implement the flipped classroom model does not work effectively.

However, exceptions are always there. The Barefoot College in Rajasthan has been experimenting the flipped classroom model using low-cost solar-powered tablets. The use of these solar power tablets helps in functioning of flipped classroom. These devices allow students in remote areas to access learning materials offline. Thus, implementation in rural areas need to be more focused and demand more options to work in odd situation too. Therefore, flipped classrooms could function well even in resource-poor areas (Rao, 2020).

ADVANTAGES OF FLIPPED CLASSROOMS IN INDIAN SCENARIO

- **Increased Student Participation:** As students go through the content before coming to class and understand at their own. They have their sets of doubts and clarity, using which they can participate more actively in discussions, experimentation and peer learning activities. Thus, student's role shift from passive learner to active learner. Student willingly participate in learning activities of the class that shows improvements in student engagement in Indian schools (Tiwari & Shah, 2021).
- **Individualized Learning:** In flipped classroom model, students learn and understand Online or offline learning material with their own pace and knowledge. After that they take part in discussions and collaborative learning activities and clear their doubts which is particularly beneficial for students with different learning styles and abilities (Bergmann & Sams, 2012). Thus, this personalized approach is very helpful in making students independent learner.
- **Development of Higher Learning Skills:** The flipped classroom model enhances higher-order thinking skills in students as they involved in discussions, debates, and problem-solving learning activities during class time. This is an advantage in the Indian context, where the students focus more on memorization of fundamental concepts which overshadowed critical thinking (Hwang & Lai, 2016).
- **Teacher as facilitator:** Flipped classroom model changes the role of teacher as facilitator of learning. Teachers involves in dynamic classroom interactions and act as facilitators rather than simply delivering content. This shift encourages teachers to adopt more interactive and innovative teaching strategies and also enhance their professional skills (Sharma & Ghosh, 2019).
- **Meets Classroom Diversity:** India is country having unity in diversity. In India school students comes from various cultural and language background. Classroom diversity includes students of different IQ. In flipped classroom model every student learn at their own pace by rewind and revise the content. They also convert the material in his or her language for better understanding of concepts.
- **Independent learning:** In traditional method, students passively learn what teachers taught. Very few students take part in learning process. In flipped classroom model, students independently learn out of the class and take part in discussions and collaborative learning activities in class time. Thus , flipped learning makes students independent learner.

CHALLENGES IN THE INDIAN CONTEXT

Despite the various advantages of flipped classroom model, there are several challenges that need to be taken into consideration for the successful implementation of the flipped learning in Indian schools:

- **Technological Barriers:** Several schools in rural and remote areas of India lack the necessary technological infrastructure like computers, projectors, printer and speedy internet connections. So, technological facilities need to be addressed for proper implementation of the flipped classroom model (Tiwari & Shah, 2021).
- **Infrastructure Barriers:** Several schools in rural and remote areas of India lack necessary infrastructural facilities for proper installation of digital devices. Various building need renovation and several demand the new one for effective use and implementation of flipped classrooms.
- **Teacher Training:** Teachers in Indian schools are not adequately trained to use digital tools in classrooms. Professional development programs for effective usage of digital devices are needed for proper implementation of flipped learning pedagogy. Thus, digital literacy is essential for teachers for the success flipped classroom model (Rao, 2020).
- **Student Readiness:** Students of urban schools are more familiar with digital devices and are accustomed to use these in learning. But students in rural areas are not accustomed to use these digital devices online for learning. Thus, when something new will be experimented they are not ready to do so. They did not take the learning seriously because of lack of proper digital resources. Therefore, the effectiveness of the flipped classroom model may lack due to the readiness of students (Sharma & Ghosh, 2019).
- **Traditional Mindset:** The traditional culture of learning in Indian education system is teacher-centered. The work of teacher is to teach and student follows the same. This old system create resistance to adopt any new approach such as the flipped classroom model. Both students and teachers follow rigidly the traditional approach. To overcome this old mindset requires time, awareness, interest, motivation and continuous effort to change the whole educational practices (Tiwari & Shah, 2021).

DISCUSSION

The findings of the systematics review of literature highlights that the flipped learning has the potential to transform school education into student-centered learning. Using flipped learning the students are actively engaged and participate in the teaching learning process. However, its effectiveness is dependent on several critical issues that needs to be addressed first for proper functioning of flipped classroom model. For example, the digital divide in rural and urban areas remains a significant barrier. Income is another such barrier, since digital tools require proper upgradation and maintenance from time to time. Reliable internet connectivity also requires to go through the online content such as videos, ppt etc. (Kim et al., 2014).

The success of flipped learning depends highly on teacher readiness and capabilities to develop quality instructional materials. Thus, analysis of literature highlights the need of professional development programs for teachers to equip them with necessary skills. Teachers should have ability to create engaging content so as to manage flipped classrooms effectively (Bergmann & Sams, 2012).

The review also reveals gaps in the literature. Since most of the studies are done in foreign countries, research in Indian context need to be addressed. The most of the studies found the impact of flipped learning on STEM subjects, there are limited research done on the applications of flipped learning in humanities and arts. Moreover, most studies are short-term, focusing on immediate outcomes rather than long-term impacts (Lo & Hew, 2017).

FUTURE CHALLENGES AND DIRECTIONS

1. Equity in Access

Ensuring equitable access to technology is a critical issue that need to be addressed. Policymakers and educators should work together to provide such schemes so that digital devices and internet connectivity will be accessible to all students in all areas. If public-private partnerships should work hand in hand than this issue will no longer a critical one. Government initiatives could play a pivotal role in making all digital resources accessibility in remote regions too (Chen et al., 2018).

2. Teacher Training and Support

Comprehensive professional training programs to prepare high quality learning material for the students learning are essential for the flipped classroom model. These programs should focus on content creation and classroom management with new techniques to engage students. Government should plan such programmes from time to time for proper upgradation of teachers with technological advancement (Kim et al., 2014).

3. Curriculum Integration

Integrating curriculum to accommodate flipped learning remains a challenge in Indian scenario. Curriculum developers must ensure that flipped learning approaches align with learning methodologies and assessment frameworks of Indian schools. Educational policies should support the integration of technology and innovative pedagogies in the classroom (Sharma & Ghosh, 2019). Policymakers should plan curriculum framework in such a way that it has flexibility to adopt such new pedagogical advancement in Indian scenario (Lo & Hew, 2017).

4. Integration of New Technology

Emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), augmented reality (AR), and virtual reality (VR) have the potential to enhance flipped learning. Thus, future research should be done on these technologies that how they can be integrated into flipped classrooms model (van Eck & Waltman, 2010).

5. Research Recommendations

Future research studies should address the following gaps:

- Longitudinal research to assess the long-term impacts of flipped learning.
- Greater focus on rural areas.
- Impact of flipped learning on Humanities and Arts.
- Integration of flipped learning with other new pedagogical models.
- Effect of flipped learning on student outcomes, engagement and retention.

CONCLUSION

The flipped classroom model has great potential to revolutionize education system in Indian schools. This model had notable effect on students' overall development as it is a student-centered approach that stimulate active participation, higher order thinking, and individualized education. Although there are various challenges like infrastructure, teacher training, and cultural resistance but flipped classroom model provide numerous opportunities to leverage the benefits in both urban and rural contexts. Thus, investment in technological usage, teacher professional development, and curriculum integration will widespread the adoption of the flipped classroom in India. Adoption of flipped classroom model helps in addressing some of the longstanding issues within the Indian education system.

This systematic review highlights the need for continued research and collaboration among educators, policymakers, and researchers to utilize the noteworthy potential of flipped learning. Therefore, flipped learning can play a pivotal role in shaping the school education of Indian schools.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to extend our heartfelt gratitude to the Government of Uttar Pradesh for the financial support provided to our project entitled “*A Study of the Effect of Flipped Teaching on Academic Performance and Self- Efficacy of Students in Mathematics*” under the Research and Development (R&D) program 2023-24. This review paper is a part of the abovementioned Project.

REFERENCES

- 1) Bergmann, J., & Sams, A. (2012). *Flip Your Classroom: Reach Every Student in Every Class Every Day*. International Society for Technology in Education.
- 2) 2.Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.
- 3) 3.Chen, F., Wang, T., & Kirschner, P. A. (2018). The flipped classroom in K-12 education: A meta-analysis. *Educational Research Review*, 28, 39-50.
- 4) 4. Dutta, R., Mantri, A., Singh, G., & Singh, N. P. (2023). Measuring the impact of augmented reality in flipped learning mode on critical thinking, learning motivation, and knowledge of engineering students. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 32(6), 912–930. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10956-023-10051-2>
- 5) 5. Farooqi, S., & Naeem, F. (2023). Precedence and Impact of Flipped Classroom on Student Engagement: Mediating Study Using SEM-PLS. *Advanced Education*, 11(23), 52–68. <https://doi.org/10.20535/2410-8286.272234>
- 6) 4. Hwang, G. J., & Lai, C. L. (2016). A flipped classroom model based on the integration of multiple learning strategies: A case study in an engineering course. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 64(2), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-016-9454-7>.
- 7) 5. Evan Eck, N. J., & Waltman, L. (2010). Software survey: VOSviewer, a computer program for bibliometric mapping. *Scientometrics*, 84(2), 523-538.
- 8) 6.Kim, M. K., Kim, S. M., Khera, O., & Getman, J. (2014). The experience of three flipped classrooms in an urban high school. *Journal of Educational Technology Development and Exchange*, 7(2), 17-35.
- 9) 7.Lo, C. K., & Hew, K. F. (2017). The impact of flipped classrooms on student achievement in K-12 settings: A meta-analysis. *Educational Research Review*, 22, 19-33.
- 10) 8.Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J., Altman, D. G., & The PRISMA Group. (2009). Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: The PRISMA statement. *PLoS Medicine*, 6(7), e1000097.
- 11) 9. Rao, P. (2020). Flipped learning: Enhancing student engagement in Indian higher education. *Education and Information Technologies*, 25(4), 2999-3015. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-020-03391-9>.
- 12) 10. Sharma, R., & Ghosh, R. (2019). Flipped classrooms in Indian K-12 schools: Opportunities and challenges. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 16(1), 34-47. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-019-0170-1>

- 13) 11. Tiwari, R., & Shah, A. (2021). Investigating the effectiveness of flipped classrooms in engineering education in India. *Higher Education*, 81(6), 1189-1205. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-020-00578-5>.
- 14) 12. Wang Binhong. (2014). The Application of Flipped Classroom in College English Teaching. *College English*, 1, 9-12.
- 15) 13. Wang Hong. (2013). The Design of Flipped Classroom Teaching Model—Analysis Based on Typical Cases at Home and Abroad. *Modern Educational Technology*, 8, 5-10.
- 16) 14. Wang Xiaodong, Zhang Chenjingzi. (2011). The Application Research of Flipped Classroom in University Teaching—A case study on professional English of Educational Technology. *Modern Educational Technology*, 8, 11-16.
- 17) 15. Zainuddin, Z., & Perera, C. (2019). The flipped classroom: A review of its application in education. *Educational Media International*, 56(4), 280-295. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09523987.2019.1671402>.
- 18) 16. Zhang Futao. (2014). *Flipped Class Model: Theoretical Research and Practical Exploration*. Jinan: Shandong Friendship Press.
- 19) 17. Zhang Jinlei. (2013). An Analysis on the Key Factors of Flipped Classroom Teaching Model. *Distance Education in China*, 10, 59-64.
- 20) 18. Zhang Renxian. (2014). *Flipping Classroom Model and Teaching Transition*. Beijing: World Knowledge Press.
- 21) 19. Zhong Xiaoliu, Song Shuqiang, Jiao Lizhen. (2013). *Instructional Design Based on the Idea of the Flipped Classroom in ICT* © 2019